

EDUCATION SYSTEM IN COVID-19 PANDEMIC: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT: Most government the world has temporarily closed education institution in an attempt to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. These nationwide closure are impacting over 90% of the world's student population and impacting millions additional learners.COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered corona virus. To overcome from this crisis we should adopted open source digital learning solution Radio and T.V. are also very powerful tool and social networks what's app can communicate effectively with the parents and teachers and provide guidelines to the learning process. In this pandemic teachers should map the e-learning environments and e-tools you use for distance learning in your school.

COVID-19 is also change the system of education for our young learner. We will educate the learner in an inter connected world. We should redefining the role of the educator and develop teaching life skill needed for future. Education institution should unlock technology to deliver education. As education systems cope with this crisis, they must also be thinking of how they can recover stronger, with a renewed sense of responsibility of all actors and with a better understanding and sense of urgency of the need to close the gap in opportunities and assuring that all children have the same chances for a quality education.

KEYWORD- Education, COVID-19, Challenges, Strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is first and foremost a health crisis. Many countries have decided to close schools, colleges and universities. The severe short-term disruption is felt by many families around the world: home schooling is not only a massive shock to parent's productivity, but also to children's social life and learning. Teaching is moving online, on an untested and unprecedented scale. Student assessments are also moving online, with a lot of trial and error and uncertainty for everyone. Importantly, these interruptions will not just be a short-term issue, but can also have long-term consequences for the affected cohorts and are likely to increase inequality.¹

The structure of schooling and learning, including teaching and assessment methodologies, was the first to be affected by these closures. Only a handful of private schools could adopt online teaching methods. Their low-income private and government school counterparts, on the other hand, have completely shut down for not having access to **e-learning** solutions. The students, in addition to the missed opportunities for learning, no longer have access to healthy meals during this time and are subject to economic and social stress. Impact of COVID 19 on Education is going to school is the best public policy tool available to raise skills. While school time can be fun and can raised social skills and social awareness, from an economic point of view the primary point of being in school is that it increases a child's ability. Even a relatively short time in school does this; even a relatively short period of missed school will have consequences for skill growth. But can we estimate how much the COVID-19 interruption will affect learning? Not very precisely, as we are in a new world; but we can use other studies to get an order of magnitude.²

II. EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION SYSTEM

From 2019–20 corona virus pandemic has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, colleges and universities.

Approximately 1.723 billion **learners** have been affected due to school closures in response to the pandemic. According to UNESCO monitoring, 189 countries have implemented nationwide closures and 5 have implemented local closures, impacting about 98.4 percent of the world's student population. School closures

impact not only students, teachers and families but have far-reaching economic and societal consequences. The impact was more severe for disadvantaged children and their families, causing interrupted learning, compromised nutrition, childcare problems, and consequent economic cost to families who could not work. In response to school closures, UNESCO recommended the use of distance learning programs and open educational applications and platforms that schools and teachers can use to reach learners remotely and limit the disruption of education.

The majority of data collected on the number of students and learners impacted by COVID-19 had been calculated based on the closure of formal education systems. The UNESCO Institute for Statistics provides figures on students impacted by COVID-19 corresponding to the number of learners enrolled at pre-primary, primary, lower-secondary, and upper-secondary levels of education , as well as at tertiary education levels.³

Families are central to education and are widely agreed to provide major inputs into a child's learning. The current global-scale expansion in home schooling might at first thought be seen quite positively, as likely to be effective. But typically, this role is seen as a complement to the input from school. Being the prime driver of learning, even in conjunction with online materials, is a different question; and while many parents round the world do successfully school their children at home, this seems unlikely to generalize over the whole population.⁴

III. EDUCATIONAL CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF CORONA VIRUS COVID-19 PANDEMIC

We are living amidst what is potentially one of the greatest threats in our lifetime to global education, a gigantic educational crisis. As of March 28, 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic is causing more than 1.6 billion children and youth to be out of school in 161 countries. We were already experiencing a global leaning crisis, as many students were in school, but were not learning the fundamental skills needed for life.

What should we be worried about in this phase of the crisis that might have an immediate impact on children and youth?

(1) Losses in learning

(2) Increased dropout rates

(3) Children missing their most important meal of the day.

Moreover, most countries have very unequal education systems, and these negative impacts will be felt disproportionately by poor children. When it rains, it pours for them.

3.1 Learning- Starting the school year late or interrupting it completely disrupts the lives of many children, their parents, and teachers. A lot can be done to at least reduce the impact through remote learning strategies. In middle-income and poorer countries, the situation is very mixed and if we do not act appropriately, the vast inequality of opportunities that exists – egregious and unacceptable to start with – will be amplified. Many children do not have a desk, books, internet connectivity, a laptop at home, or supportive parents. Others do. What we need to avoid – or minimize as much as possible – is for those differences in opportunities to expand and cause the crisis to have an even larger negative effect on poor children’s learning.

Radio and TV are also very powerful tools. The advantage we have Today, is that through social networks, What’s App or SMS, ministries of education can communicate effectively with parents and teachers and provide guidelines, instructions and structure to the learning process, using content delivered by radio or TV. Remote learning is not only about online learning, but about mixed media learning, with the objective of reaching as many students as possible, today.

3.2 Staying engaged- Maintaining the engagement of children. Dropout rates are still very high in many countries, and a long period of disengagement can result in a further increase. Going to school is not only about learning math and science, but also about social relationships and peer-to-peer interactions. It is about learning to be a citizen and developing social skills. That is why it is important to stay connected with the school by any means necessary. For all students, this is also a time to develop socio-emotional skills and learn more about how to contribute to society as a citizen.

IV. EDUCATIONAL STRATEGY IN COVID-19 PANDEMIC

A multi-pronged strategy is necessary to manage the crisis and build a resilient Indian education system in the long term.

One, immediate measures are essential to ensure continuity of learning in government schools and universities. Open-source digital learning solutions and Learning Management Software should be adopted so teachers can conduct teaching online. The [DIKSHA platform](#), with reach across all states in India, can be further strengthened to ensure accessibility of learning to the students.

Two, inclusive learning solutions, especially for the most vulnerable and marginalized, need to be developed.

With a rapid increase of mobile internet users in India, which is expected to reach 85% households by 2024, technology is enabling ubiquitous access and personalization of education even in the remotest parts of the country. This can change the schooling system and increase the effectiveness of learning and teaching, giving students and teachers multiple options to choose from.

Three, strategies are required to prepare the higher education sector for the evolving demand–supply trends across the globe—particularly those related to the global mobility of students and faculty and improving the quality of and demand for higher studies in India.

Four, it is also important to reconsider the current delivery and pedagogical methods in school and higher education by seamlessly integrating classroom learning with e-learning modes to build a unified learning system. The major challenge in **ED Tech** reforms at the national level is the seamless integration of technology in the present Indian education system, which is the most diverse and largest in the world with more than 15 lakhs schools and 50,000 higher education institutions. Further, it is also important to establish quality assurance mechanisms and quality benchmark for online learning developed and offered by India HEIs as well as e-learning platforms (growing rapidly). Many e-learning players offer multiple courses on the same subjects with different levels of certifications, methodology and assessment parameters. So, the quality of courses may differ across different e-learning platforms.

V. HOW CORONA VIRUS CHANGE EDUCATION OF OUR GENERATION?

The COVID-19 crisis may well change our world and our global outlook; it may also teach us about how education needs to change to be able to better prepare our young learners for what the future might hold. These lessons include:

5.1. Educating citizens in an interconnected world

COVID-19 is a pandemic that illustrates how globally interconnected we are – there is no longer such a thing as isolated issues and actions. Successful people in the coming decades need to be able to understand this interrelatedness and navigate across boundaries to leverage their differences and work in a globally collaborative way.

5.2. Redefining the role of the educator

The notion of an educator as the knowledge-holder who imparts wisdom to their pupils is no longer fit for the purpose of a 21st century education. With students being able to gain access to knowledge, and even learn a technical skill, through a few clicks on their phones, tablets and computers, we will need to redefine the role of the educator in the classroom and lecture theatre. This may mean that the role of educators will need to move towards facilitating young people's development as contributing members of society.

5.3. Teaching life skills needed for the future

In this ever-changing global environment, young people require resilience and adaptability – skills that are proving to be essential to navigate effectively through this pandemic. Looking into the future, some of the most important skills that employers will be looking for will be creativity, communication and collaboration, alongside empathy and emotional intelligence; and being able to work across demographic lines of differences to harness the power of the collective through effective teamwork.

5.4. Unlocking technology to deliver education

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in educational institutions across the world being compelled to suddenly harness and utilize the suite of available technological tools to create content for remote learning for students in all sectors. Educators across the world are experiencing new possibilities to do things differently and with greater flexibility resulting in potential benefits in accessibility to education for students across the world.⁵

CONCLUSION

In this time of crisis, a well-rounded and effective educational practice is what is needed for the capacity-building of young minds. It will develop skills that will drive their employability, productivity, health, and well-being in the decades to come, and ensure the overall progress.

Some countries will be able to increase their teachers' digital skills. Radio and TV stations will recognize their key role in supporting national education goals – and hopefully, improve the quality of their programming understanding their immense social responsibility.

The mission of all education systems is the same. It is to overcome the learning crisis we were already living and respond to the pandemic we are all facing. The challenge today is to reduce as much as possible the negative impact this pandemic will have on learning and schooling and build on this experience to get back on a path of faster improvement in learning. As education systems cope with this crisis, they must also be thinking of how they can recover stronger, with a renewed sense of responsibility of all actors and with a better understanding and sense of urgency of the need to close the gap in opportunities and assuring that all children have the same chances for a quality education.

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